

Dihydrogen Reduction of Nitroaromatics in Presence of Nickel(II), Palladium(II), and Platinum(II) Acetylacetonates in Homogeneous Phase

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Dihydrogen reductions of nitroaromatics have been studied in presence of $[M(acac)_n]_n$, where, acac=acetylacetonate anion; $M=Ni$, $n=3$; $M=Pd, Pt$, $n=1$, under normal pressure conditions. Palladium(II) complex was more active than its platinum(II) analogue while nickel(II) complex was inactive. An intermediate deep green compound of composition $[Pd(acac)(acacH)H(C_6H_5NO_2)]_n$ was isolated during nitrobenzene reduction. Partially reduced nitroarenes could further be reduced in presence on nitrobenzene only. The initial reduction rate was found to be first order dependent on each of hydrogen pressure and catalyst concentration, and independent of substrate concentration. A rate equation of the form, initial rate $=k[catalyst][H_2]$, has been derived and the reduction mechanism has been discussed on the basis of experimental results and kinetic data.

HOMOGENEOUS reductions of nitroarenes have been investigated by several workers using various reducing agents such as H_2 , (H_2+CO) etc. in presence of transition metal complexes¹⁻⁵. The importance of these reductions lies in the industrial use of their reduction products. In many cases, higher temperatures and super atmospheric pressures have been used for successful reductions⁶. Detailed kinetic studies are lacking in most cases due to non-reproducibility of the data and decomposition of the catalysts during reduction. Complexes used for this reduction process generally contained π -acid ligands such as PPh_3 , py, quinoline etc., and very few of them contained π -basic ligands⁷. Electrophilic substitution reaction on metal acetylacetonates suggested the ligand to be π -basic and the presence of ring current in the metal chelates⁸. It is, therefore, interesting to investigate the catalytic activities of metal complexes with this ligand. This paper reports the catalytic activities of d^8 -metal acetylacetonates towards the dihydrogen reduction of nitroaromatics.

Experimental

Analytical grade reagents and pure and freshly distilled solvents were used throughout the work. Hydrogen gas was purified as described elsewhere⁹. The complexes $Ni_3(acac)_6$, $Pd(acac)_2$ and $Pt(acac)_2$, used as catalysts in the present investigation were prepared and purified according to known procedures¹⁰⁻¹². Vibrational, electronic and pmr spectral studies were made in Perkin-Elmer Infracord, Cary 17D and EM 390, 90 MHz spectrophotometers, respectively.

Catalytic hydrogenation: Catalytic hydrogenation was carried out in a 50 ml reaction flask which

was first evacuated and then purged several times with nitrogen prior to introduction of hydrogen. Dry and pure nitrogen was bubbled through the methanolic solution (15 ml) of the appropriate nitroarene and the catalyst for 15 min and the solution was then introduced into the reaction flask under hydrogen. A blank methanolic solution of the same nitroarene was connected to the experimental setup in order to eliminate the solution vapour pressure. Both the solutions were stirred vigorously. There was no appreciable gas absorption at the beginning. In case of $Pd(acac)_2$, a deep green precipitate appeared within 20–30 min which dissolved quickly to produce a deep green solution. The rate of gas absorption which was maximum at this stage decreased slowly and stopped at the end. In case of $Ni_3(acac)_6$, neither the change of solution colour nor the reductions of nitroarenes occurred. $Pt(acac)_2$ produced a faint precipitate and the reduction rate was much slow compared to its palladium(II) analogue. All attempts to isolate the catalytic species from the final green solution failed. However, addition of fresh nitroarene to the final green solution restored the hydrogen absorption almost to initial rate. The process could be repeated several times without appreciable loss of catalytic activity. However, the catalyst underwent slow decomposition on keeping the final solution mixture for several days under nitrogen or hydrogen.

Isolation of the deep green compound: The deep green precipitate formed during catalytic run was filtered and washed with ether under nitrogen and dried in vacuum. The compound was diamagnetic, highly sensitive to moisture and decomposed in solution. Chemical analysis approximately

corresponds to the formula Pd(acac)(acacH)H (C₆H₅NO₂). Ir spectra exhibit peaks at 2138 (Pd-H), 655 and 442 (Pd-O) and 1540 cm⁻¹ (NO₂ coordinated) in addition to other peaks due to acac group. No peak due to $\nu_{\text{Pd-C}}$ was observed. The solution of the compound in DMSO-D₆ decomposes during pmr spectral run. However, the signals due to acetylacetone and nitrobenzene in the intensity ratio as required for the suggested formula are found in the pmr spectra. Quick dissolution of the compound during the catalytic run suggests it to be dimeric six-coordinated in the solid state (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

Separation and estimation of the products : The liquid components of the final product mixture were separated by fractional distillation. The residue left was extracted with benzene and the components were separated by column chromatography using silica gel column and benzene as eluant. These were finally estimated by glc using SE-30 and carbowax 20 M column. The components formed at the intermediate stages were identified and estimated by injecting ~10⁻⁸ ml of the solution mixture into the glc apparatus.

Results and Discussion

Pd(acac)₂ is more active than either its nickel(II) or platinum(II) analogues and this trend has been observed in many cases⁴. The stabilities of the catalytic intermediates containing M-H bonds are

most important for these hydrogenation reactions. The intermediate formed from the palladium(II) complex probably has the appropriate stability for the best catalytic activity. The intermediates obtained from nickel(II) or platinum(II) complexes are too unstable or stable, respectively, to have good catalytic activities.

The catalysts, though active in reducing mononitroarenes failed to reduce the dinitroarenes under the experimental conditions. The final products are the corresponding anilines (95%) for *o*-nitroarenes, and anilines (90%) and azobenzenes (10%) for other substrates. Initial rates of reduction and the percentage yields of products for different substrates are presented in Table 1.

Methanol was the best solvent for reduction and the rate decreased in higher alcohols. No appreciable reduction occurred in non-coordinating mediums like benzene, toluene or in strong coordinating solvents like DMF, DMSO. In the former case, the catalyst underwent decomposition to deposit Pd⁰ while in the latter case, it remained unaltered. Pd(acac)₂ is actually the catalyst precursor and a number of catalytic intermediates with varying stabilities are formed in solution during preliminary hydrogen treatment. Some of these species probably require mild coordinating and hydrogen bonding solvents for their stabilisations and therefore, decompose in non-coordinating solvents like C₆H₆, C₆H₅CH₃. Many Pd^{II} complexes with π -acid ligands are active in DMF medium^{1-3,5}. DMF coordinates using its C=O π -orbitals^{1,3} and therefore, behaves as a weak π -acid ligand in presence of stronger π -acid ligands in the complex. In the presence of π -basic ligand, it becomes a stronger π -acid ligand and hence its displacement from the coordination sphere by substrate molecule is not feasible. This factor probably prevents the reduction of the substrates in these solvents.

The reaction is greatly influenced in presence of acids or alkali. In presence of alkali (10⁻³ M), the catalyst solution turned brown at the beginning and the reduction started with simultaneous decomposition of the catalyst. Addition of small amount of

TABLE 1—DIHYDROGEN REDUCTION OF NITROAROMATICS BY Pd(acac)₂ AS HOMOGENEOUS CATALYST

Catalyst concn. = 2.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, Substrate concn. = 0.2 mol dm⁻³, Temp = 30°, Pressure = 760 mm/Hg, Volume of the reacting solution = 15 ml, Solvent = methanol

Sl. no.	Substrates	Initial rate of hydrogen uptake ml min ⁻¹	Induction period min	Products (mol %)
1.	<i>p</i> -Nitrotoluene	6.5	20	<i>p</i> -Toluidine(92), <i>p</i> -Azotoluene(5)
2.	<i>p</i> -Nitroaniline	7.0	15	<i>p</i> -Phenylenediamine(85), PolymeI(10)
3.	Nitrobenzene	6.2	20	Aniline(95), Azobenzene(2.5)
4.	<i>p</i> -Chloronitrobenzene	5.8	20	<i>p</i> -Chloroaniline(65), Azo-compound(20)
5.	<i>m</i> -Chloronitrobenzene	5.2	20	<i>m</i> -Chloroaniline(70), Azo-compound(20)
6.	<i>m</i> -Nitroaniline	3.5	15	<i>m</i> -Phenylenediamine(92)
7.	<i>o</i> -Chloronitrobenzene	3.2	25	<i>o</i> -Chloroaniline(92)
8.	<i>o</i> -Nitroaniline	3.0	30	<i>o</i> -Phenylenediamine(90)
9.	<i>o</i> -Nitrotoluene	2.5	30	<i>o</i> -Toluidine(95)
10.	2,5-Nitroxylene	0.4	40	Not characterised.

acid (CH_3COOH , HCl , $10^{-3} M$) increased the induction period and decreased the reduction rate slightly without altering the nature and yields of the final products. However, the reduction stopped in presence of higher concentrations of acids ($0.1 M$). The reduction mechanism in neutral or acid medium is therefore different from that in alkaline medium. The nature and position of the substituents have great influence on the reduction rate and the nature of the products formed. Electron-releasing substituents enhance the reduction rate. The order of increasing rate with the nature of the *para*-substituents is $\text{Cl} > \text{H} > \text{CH}_3 > \text{NH}_2$ (Table 1.). Dinitrobenzenes and nitrobenzaldehydes are not reduced at all. The presence of appreciable electron density on the NO_2 group is probably essential for its coordination to the metal and hence the reduction to occur. In dinitrobenzenes and nitrobenzaldehydes, lower electron density on the NO_2 group does not allow its coordination to the metal with sufficient stability for the reduction to occur.

The reduction rates of *ortho*-substituted-nitroarenes are much lower and decrease with the bulkiness of the substituents; $\text{Cl} > \text{NH}_2 > \text{CH}_3$. 2,5-Nitroxyloxy is reduced at a very slow rate. The reduction products of nitrobenzene and its *para*-substituted derivatives contained small amount of azoxy- and azo-compound in addition to anilines, whereas no such products were detected at any stage during the reduction of *ortho*-compounds (Figs. 1 and 2; Table 1). Steric hindrance probably

Fig. 1. Reduction products of nitrobenzene at various time intervals; $[\text{Pd}(\text{acac})_2] = 1.95 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NO}_2] = 0.25 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$: (○) aniline, (□) nitrobenzene, (Δ) Azoxybenzene, and (●) azobenzene.

resists the coordination of the *ortho*-compounds and thus decreases the stabilities and hence concentrations of 'metal-substrate' intermediates. This leads to lower reduction rate. Similarly, simultaneous coordinations of two *ortho*-substituted molecules *cis*- to the metal atom is prevented by steric reasons and so no azo- or azoxy-products are formed. Preferential reductions were observed only in case of the mixtures of *ortho*- and *para*-substituted-nitroarenes. Formations of *ortho*-substituted-anilines were detected only after the formations (60–90%) of *para*-substituted-anilines. Due

Fig. 2. Reduction products of *o*-nitrotoluene (A) and *o*-chloronitrobenzene (B) at various time intervals, for (A), $[\text{Pd}(\text{acac})_2] = 2.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{o-CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NO}_2] = 0.35 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$: (○) *o*-CH₃C₆H₄NH₂, and (□) *o*-CH₃C₆H₄NO₂; for (B), $[\text{Pd}(\text{acac})_2] = 2.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{o-ClC}_6\text{H}_4\text{NO}_2] = 0.2 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$: (Δ) *o*-ClC₆H₄NH₂, and (●) *o*-ClC₆H₄NO₂.

to higher stabilities, the concentrations of 'metal-substrate' intermediates for *para*-substituted compounds far exceeds that of *ortho*-substituted ones. This results in the observed preferential reductions. In case of almost equal stabilities of the two species, their concentrations in the solution would have been comparable. Under this condition, different values of rate constants, k as shown in Scheme 2, would lead to the simultaneous formation of both types of anilines at unequal rates.

$\text{Pd}(\text{acac})_2$ (PPh_3)Cl containing both π -acid and π -basic ligands in it is inactive for this reduction process. The presence of both these types of ligands makes the complex relatively more stable with mutually strengthened metal–ligand bonds and less susceptible to substrate coordination. Neither the formation of active catalytic species by dissociation of a ligand nor the coordination of nitroaromatics to the metal appears probable. The complex, therefore, becomes catalytically inactive.

The composition of reaction mixture at various time intervals for nitrobenzene reduction is presented in Fig. 1. It appears that azobenzene is formed from the reduction of azoxybenzene and this has been confirmed by independent experiment. Initial addition of aniline ($2 M$) during nitrobenzene reduction increased the proportion of azoxybenzene at intermediate stages and azobenzene at the end. This supports the formation of coupled products in the coordination sphere only. Azobenzene could not be reduced by these complexes.

Passing of hydrogen through the methanolic solution of $\text{M}(\text{acac})_2$ ($\text{M} = \text{Pd}, \text{Pt}$) containing $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NO}$, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NHOH}$, or $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{N}(\text{O}) = \text{NC}_6\text{H}_5$ did neither produce the deep green precipitate nor reduce these substrates. However, addition of

small amount of nitrobenzene (0.01 M) started the reduction of these substrates following all the usual changes. $M(acac)_2$ is, therefore, not the actual catalyst but a catalyst precursor. The actual catalyst present in the green solution is formed from $[Pd(acac)(acacH)(C_6H_5NO_2)H]_2$ under the experimental condition.

A tentative mechanism has been suggested for the formation of most active intermediate (A).

The π -type of bonding between palladium(II) and nitroarene is probably responsible for the cleavage of one Pd-acac bond leading to the formation of most active intermediate (A). Partially reduced nitroarenes such as C_6H_5NO , C_6H_5NHOH or $C_6H_5N(O)=NC_6H_5$ are unable to form this type of π -bonding and therefore can neither produce (A) nor are reduced by these catalysts.

Reduction of only nitrobenzene in presence of $Pd(acac)_2$ has been studied previously⁷. The sequence of colour changes and the nature of the final products obtained by using the above system suggest its reduction mechanism to be different from the present one.

Kinetic studies: Kinetic studies were made only with *o*-chloronitrobenzene and *o*-nitrotoluene using $Pd(acac)_2$ at 30° in dry methanol medium (15 ml). The *ortho*-substituted compounds produced only the corresponding anilines and therefore

complications involved due to the formations of coupled products were avoided. The initial rates of reductions were found to be first order dependent on catalyst concentrations in the range of $0.5-4.5 \times 10^{-3}$ mol dm⁻³ and hydrogen pressure in the range of 200–1 000 mm of Hg, and independent of substrate concentrations in the range of 0.1–0.6 mol dm⁻³ (Figs. 3, 4 and 5). The initial rates of reductions were also studied in presence corresponding anilines in order to find out their involvements in coordination with the metal atom. The rates were found to be inversely dependent on the concentrations of initially added anilines. On the basis of experimental results, a tentative mechanism has been suggested for this reduction process (Scheme 2). The coupled products may be formed otherwise also. (D) may have trigonal bipyramidal configuration with hydrogen *trans* to RNO_2 . In case of reductions of *ortho*-substituted compounds, species (A), (B) and (C) are involved while the

Fig. 3. Rate dependence on catalyst concentrations; H_2 -pressure=1 atm; for (A), $[o-ClC_6H_4NO_2]=0.2$ mol dm⁻³; (○) $o-ClC_6H_4NH_2$, for (B), $[o-CH_3C_6H_4NO_2]=0.35$ mol dm⁻³; (□) $o-CH_3C_6H_4NH_2$.

Fig. 4. Rate dependence on H_2 -pressure; $[Pd(acac)_2]=2.0 \times 10^{-3}$ mol dm⁻³; for (A), $[o-ClC_6H_4NO_2]=0.2$ mol dm⁻³; (○) $o-ClC_6H_4NH_2$; for (B), $[o-CH_3C_6H_4NO_2]=0.35$ mol dm⁻³; (□) $o-CH_3C_6H_4NH_2$.

Fig. 5. Rate dependence on substrate concentrations; $[Pd(acac)_2] = 2.0 \times 10^{-3}$ mol dm $^{-3}$; for (A), $[o-ClC_6H_4NO_2] = 0.2$ mol dm $^{-3}$; (Δ) $o-ClC_6H_4NH_2$; for (B), $[o-OH_2C_6H_4NO_2] = 0.35$ mol dm $^{-3}$; ($\circ$) $o-OH_2C_6H_4NH_2$.

other species may be present during the reduction of other substrates. The electronic spectra of the methanolic solution of $Pd(acac)_2$ exhibit peaks at 644 and 500(sh) nm while that of the green solution shows peaks at 600(w), 520(sh) and 400(sh) nm in the visible region indicating the complete absence of $Pd(acac)_2$ in the catalytically active green solution. Independent experiment showed the rate of reduction of nitrosobenzene to be 5–6 times faster than that of $C_6H_5NO_2$. Hence, the concentration of [B] was neglected during the derivation of rate equation. Representing $[RNO_2]$ = nitroarene concentration, $[RNH_2]$ = aniline concentration, $[H_2]$ = concentration of hydrogen in methanol = $k_1[PH_2]$, where, PH_2 = hydrogen pressure, and $[Cat]_T$ = total catalyst concentration.

From Scheme 2,

$$\text{Rate} = k[A][H_2]$$

$[Cat] = [A] + [C]$ as the concentration of B was considered negligible.

$$K = \frac{[A][RNH_2]}{[C][RNO_2]}$$

$$[A] = \frac{K[Cat]_T[RNO_2]}{K[RNO_2] + [RNH_2]}$$

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{kK[Cat]_T[RNO_2][H_2]}{K[RNO_2] + [RNH_2]} \quad (1)$$

At the beginning when $[RNH_2] \approx 0$,

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Initial rate} &= kK[Cat]_T[H_2] \\ &= kk_1K[Cat]_T[PH_2] \end{aligned}$$

The equation agrees with the kinetic data.

Again the rate equation in presence of aniline may be written as follows from equation (1),

$$\frac{1}{\text{rate}} = \frac{1}{k[Cat]_T[H_2]} + \frac{[RNH_2]}{kK[Cat]_T[RNO_2][H_2]}$$

The values of intercepts and slopes for these two substrates were determined from the plots of 1/rate

vs $[RNH_2]$ which is linear (Figs. 6 and 7). The intercept $\frac{1}{k[Cat]_T[H_2]}$ was found to be 4.25×10^{-3} mol dm 3 min for o -chloronitrobenzene. Putting the known values of $[Cat]_T = 2.0 \times 10^{-3}$ mol dm $^{-3}$ and $[H_2]^{14} = 3.9 \times 10^{-3}$ mol dm $^{-3}$, the value of k was found to be 3.01×10^3 mol $^{-1}$ dm 3 min $^{-1}$.

Fig. 6. Rate dependence on the concentrations of initially added o -chloroaniline, $[Pd(acac)_2] = 2.0 \times 10^{-3}$ mol dm $^{-3}$, $[o-ClC_6H_4NO_2] = 0.2$ mol dm $^{-3}$.

Fig. 7. Rate dependence on the concentration of initially added o -toluidine, $[Pd(acac)_2] = 2.5 \times 10^{-3}$ mol dm $^{-3}$, $[o-OH_2C_6H_4NO_2] = 0.35$ mol dm $^{-3}$.

Again, slope = $\frac{1}{kK[Cat]_T[RNO_2][H_2]}$ was found to be 265 mol 2 dm 6 min. Putting the known values

of $k[\text{Cat}]_T[\text{H}_2]$ and $[\text{RNO}_2]=0.2 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, the value of K was found to be 8.03. Similarly, the values of k and K for *o*-nitrotoluene were calculated to be $2.27 \times 10^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ min}$ and 15.49, respectively. Comparison of the values of rate constants for these two substrates indicates that *o*-chloronitrobenzene should be reduced faster than *o*-nitrotoluene which is in accordance with the experiment.

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